

LARGE STRAIN COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN DEPLOYABLE SPACE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

This paper investigates large strain composite materials in deployable space structures. These structures balance material stiffness and foldability to achieve both compact packaging and efficient deployed performance. Past approaches to achieve this compromise are reviewed and new material developments are discussed. Materials are compared based on metrics for packaged and deployed structural efficiency. Structural architecture limitations are found to exist due to the low modulus and strain combination of currently available passive materials. Large strain elastomeric resin composite materials are shown to have the potential to eliminate these limitations.

Keywords: deployable structures, space structures, large strain composites

INTRODUCTION

Large strain materials have been used extensively by the deployable space structures community to build reliable and highly compactable structures such as storable tubular extendible masts (STEM)¹⁻³, continuous longeron trusses⁴ and wrap-rib reflectors^{5,6} (Figure 1). While successful, these architectures all exhibit relatively low structural hierarchy compared to alternate approaches and are limited in their potential structural performance and sizes. For example, the STEM is a tube, the continuous longeron truss is a truss of solid rods and the wrap-rib employs open-section beam elements. Increases in hierarchy, such as trusses of tubes or trusses of trusses have not achieved flight success with large strain material approaches. Such structures have been achieved with mechanical approaches employing sliding contact (pin-clevis) joints. For example, the deployable mesh reflector in Figure 2 uses complex mechanisms to form a perimeter truss of tubes⁷. A contributing factor to this state is the less than sufficient combination of modulus and strain available in traditional engineering materials as well as a poor engineering understanding of how to best exploit available materials in flexure hinge applications.

Suitable materials for large strain deployable structures must satisfy two conflicting requirements. First, the materials must be capable of large strains for compact packaging and design freedom. The architectures of Figure 1 are typically designed to 1.0-1.5% strain; however, strains of 4-5% would enable much greater design flexibility and allow the implementation of architectures that are only feasible with larger strains.

For example, the architectures in Figure 3 and Figure 4 are only possible with larger strain materials (these architectures require two to four times more strain than those in Figure 1)⁸. Second, the materials must be stiff in the deployed configuration. Space structures typically employ slender elements and shells that fail in buckling under compressive loads and the primary material property governing this load is modulus. Similarly, when loaded in tension, the material property of interest is modulus as it determines deflections and structural modes of vibration. In considering materials for deployable structures, it is important to realize that they do not need to be high modulus in the packaged configuration. It is acceptable and often desirable if the material modulus decreases during packaging so that less strain energy is stored. It is the deployed material modulus (and density) that ultimately determines the structural mass efficiency of a deployed structure. However, there is a trade between modulus for deployed performance and strain for packaging performance and materials that are good with one property are often poor with the other.

Several approaches have been researched to address this challenge. Most successful has been the development of rigidizable composite materials by L'Garde Incorporated^{9,10}, ILC Dover LP¹¹, and Composite Technology Development Incorporated^{12,13}. These companies developed carbon fiber based material systems with heat softenable matrix materials. When heated, the materials can be folded to very large strains repeatedly without degradation of their unfolded ability to resist buckling.¹⁰ The primary limitation of these materials is the extreme challenge of engineering and testing the in space heating and cooling systems they require. Either through test or analysis, demonstrating uniform and sufficient heating without excessive power requirements is highly challenging. The opposite problem of ensuring the structure remains cool enough to be rigid on orbit is equally challenging. These heating and cooling systems also have sufficient mass that the effective mass efficiency (modulus per mass metrics) of these materials is greatly reduced. As a result, rigidizable structures with both compact packaging and good deployed structural mass efficiency have rarely been achieved.

In light of these challenges, there is renewed interest in passive large strain materials: those that do not require heating, cooling or other challenging thermal restrictions. The current work investigates these materials.

Figure 1: Space deployable structures using large strain materials: a) storable tubular extendable masts¹⁻³ on Hubble Space Telescope solar arrays, b) continuous longeron mast (ATK-Able)⁴ c) Lockheed Martin wrap-rib reflector^{5,6}.

Figure 2: The Northrop Grumman Astromesh parabolic mesh reflector with truss of tubes structural hierarchy.⁷

Figure 3: Elastic loop folding proposed in Reference 8 showing single longeron and truss deployment.

Figure 4: A monolithic concertina fold architecture proposed in Reference 8.

LARGE STRAIN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Properties of materials commonly used for deployable structures are given in Table 1. These properties are the results of standardized tests and they may not be appropriate for flexure hinges (due to hinge thinness, biaxial stress states, etc.). Even so, they are used here because they are the only properties available. Firehole Technologies Incorporated's Prospector:Composites was queried for materials with relatively high strains to failure and modulus (unidirectional lamina properties in the fiber direction). Where possible, compressive modulus test results were used over tensile modulus (representing the deployed state) and flexure strain to failure was used over tensile or compressive strain to failure (representing the packed state). In the absence of flexure strain to failure data, compressive strain to failure was used. Properties of materials not represented by Prospector:Composites were derived from a combination of rule of mixtures, manufacturer data sheets and MatWeb online material database queries.

Generally desired material properties are straight forward to identify in tables of test results. Higher modulus, lower density, greater strain and greater strength are typically better. However, selection of the best material when more than one property must be considered simultaneously is not as obvious. In these cases, analytically derived metrics that are a combination of properties should be calculated to compare materials. In Reference 14, Michael Ashby tabulates many of these metrics and material properties and devises a simple logarithmic scale plot that allows consideration a several metrics at the same time. The same plot style is adopted here as the data of Table 1 are plotted in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Assessing materials for deployable structures generally requires considering more than one property at a time. In the deployed configuration, material stiffness and density are important and these are plotted in Figure 5. In parts of the structure that must deform for packaging, strain is also important and stiffness is plotted vs. strain in Figure 6. The dashed lines in these plots represent constant values for the indicated metric and can be parallel offset for greater or lower constant metric value contour lines. In the modulus vs. density plot, materials towards the upper left corner of the plot (higher modulus and lower density) are better. In the specific density vs. strain plot, materials towards the

upper right (higher modulus and larger strain) are better. The best material depends on which metric is used to assess the materials.

Dashed line slopes correspond to different metrics. In the modulus vs. density plot, four metrics are shown and one should be selected based on the application. However, regardless of metric choice, all curves tell the same story: higher modulus carbon fiber composites are best. If carbon fiber composites are neglected, proper material choice depends on the metric and application and could be either S2 fiberglass or steel.

Material selection is not as straightforward when strain is considered. As shown in Figure 6b, there is a relationship between the maximum combination of modulus and strain such that higher modulus materials have lower strain capacities and the slope of this front is parallel to the metric line $E\varepsilon^2$. Material selection is further complicated by the inappropriateness of the strain data. The deployable structures under consideration here employ flexures or solid rods that when bent to small radii, are not represented by standardized flexure or tensile tests. Further, it has been observed that thinner laminates can accommodate higher strains without failure than thicker laminates of the same material. The mechanisms for this response have not been determined, but are likely a combination of nonlinear fiber response and structural support of the laminate compressive side by the tensile side. Understanding the mechanics and failure mechanisms in large strain bending of thin composites is an area of ongoing research.

Material Metrics for Deployed Structures

Material metrics for deployed trusses in beam and column applications are derived in Reference 15. In bending applications, subscript b , the beam is designed to meet a bending stiffness requirement and a bending strength requirement (local failure of a longeron in buckling is assumed). In column applications, subscript c , the truss is designed to meet global and local longeron buckling requirements and must carry a compressive load over a length. In both cases failure is governed by buckling, which is determined from the material modulus. As a result, metrics capturing the mass efficiency of a deployed truss only involve material modulus and density (not strength). Designing the above trusses, calculating their weight equations and extracting material parameters results in the following material performance metrics,

$$\mu_b = \frac{E^{3/5}}{\rho}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_c = \frac{E^{2/3}}{\rho}. \quad (2)$$

These metrics are shown in Table 1 and Figure 5 and there is an order of magnitude difference between the stiffer and lower strain materials and the less stiff and larger strain materials. This directly translates into truss mass and even without increases in hierarchy, great improvements in truss performance can be made by simply using more efficient materials.

Metrics for non-truss cross-section beams that combine stiffness and strength are not available; however, the metric for a stiffness designed beam of arbitrary cross-section in bending is given in Reference 14 as,

$$\mu_{beam} = \frac{E^{1/2}}{\rho}. \quad (3)$$

In this metric, the beam cross-sectional shape is fixed, but it can be scaled up or down to change the cross-sectional area and it is applicable to architectures such as the STEM of Figure 1. The metric is also applicable to the buckling of columns with similar cross section constraints (e.g. a STEM used as a column).

The metric for a stiffness designed tension only tie element is,

$$\mu_{beam} = \frac{E}{\rho}. \quad (4)$$

Material Metrics for Material Deformation Base Deployable Structures

There are two common approaches to achieving efficient deployable structures. Articulated combinations of pin-clevis, ball and socket and other sliding contact joints are used in what is commonly called a mechanical approach. Second, material deformation can be used to fold a structure. Often, either approach can be used to achieve a similar deployed architecture. However, selection of deployment architecture greatly reduces freedom in material selection and ultimately, deployed performance. Deformable materials, such as S2 fiberglass reinforced epoxy are approximately four times less efficient than a high modulus material such as M60J carbon fiber reinforced epoxy. Even so, deformation based architectures have been highly successful, primarily due to their lower cost. Deformation based architectures can avoid the design, machining and assembly costs associated with having hundreds of hinges in a single deployable structure.

There are also two basic approaches to material deformation based deployable structures: distributed strain and concentrated strain. In the distributed strain approach, material deformations are distributed as uniformly as possible throughout the structure. This approach minimizes the maximum strain in the structure and is employed by the STEM and continuous longeron masts architectures of Figure 1. Rigidizable materials were developed to increase the material strain limits without sacrificing material modulus. The increased strain limits of these materials enabled more complex architectures, such as trusses of tubes, however, taking in account the reduced fiber volume fraction and mass of thermal management systems results in an effective deployed performance that is less than fiberglass. Consequently, rigidizable structures have not been able to improve on the performance obtained by mechanical or other material deformation based approaches.

In the concentrated strain approach, mechanical hinges are replaced with flexure hinges that concentrate strains into discrete hinge locations. This allows less flexible but more efficient materials to be used in the majority of the structure and the less efficient but more flexible materials are used only in hinge locations. Two concentrated strain deployable structures are shown in Figure 7.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

Simple material metrics for deformation based deployable structures based on stiffness and strength are not readily derived. When strength is neglected, stiffness driven structures become more slender and folding strains decrease; however, buckling loads quickly approach zero. Thus, placing a maximum strain requirement on stiffness driven designs tends to erroneously rate materials with lower strain limits better. This is an

artifact of strength being neglected and while strength does not often drive the design of deployable structures, metrics that include strength provide more reasonable results. The material metric for a strain limited distributed strain continuous longeron mast subjected to a bending strength requirement and weight optimized is given in Reference 8 as,

$$\mu_{clm} = \frac{(E\varepsilon)^{2/3}}{\rho}. \quad (5)$$

Metrics derived for distributed strain architectures are not necessarily applicable to concentrated strain architectures and efforts by the author to derive a simple concentrated strain metric have not yielded concise results. The primary challenge is that the goodness of a concentrated strain hinge material is always relative to the stiffer material used elsewhere in the structure. For example, a concentrated strain architecture that employs S2 fiberglass as the stiff material benefits very little from the higher modulus of a T800 composite hinge. Also, hinge axial stiffness can be more or less important depending on the cross-section of the stiffer elements in a truss. Tubes generally require less stiff materials because the decrease in cross-sectional area between a tube and a thin flexure is less than the change in cross-sectional area between a solid rod and a thin flexure. Similar relations exist with material density, though to a much lesser extent. In structures with relatively small hinges, the mass efficiency of the structure is determined primarily by the stiffer parts of the structure, not the hinges. The density of hinge materials of very high density (e.g. NiTi SMA) should not be neglected, however, in comparing high and low modulus composites with approximately the same density, this difference can be neglected.

Recognizing that a concentrated strain hinge metric should capture both material stiffness and strain and to a lesser extent density allows potential metrics to be considered. Plotting modulus vs. strain in the log-log style used thus far shows the relative importance of modulus and strain in concentrated strain architectures, Figure 8. These curves in these plots represent trusses of solid rods and trusses of tubes assembled with rectangular flexure hinges. The strut material and cross-section are labelled on each curve. The trusses were designed so that the longeron and flexure buckle at the same time in the deployed configuration and when folded, the hinge is subjected to the strain indicated by the plot. The lines are contours corresponding to a 5% decrease in truss performance due to the introduction of hinges. Hinge materials are also shown on the plots. The material data used in these plots was derived from constituent tensile properties and rule of mixtures and does not correspond to that used in Table 1. Materials that lie outward of a contour line for given architecture have more than enough modulus and strain to achieve that architecture with less than a 5% performance degradation. Materials on the inside may still work for those architectures, but more than a 5% performance degradation will occur. Lines are truncated on the left side of these plots because hinge lengths become excessively long and do not represent a concentrated strain architecture.

The curves in Figure 8 have linear regions, but they are not all the same slope. Dashed lines corresponding to potential metrics with modulus to the first power and strain to the first, second, and third power are shown. Several conclusions can be drawn from these plots. Trusses of tubes are feasible with a range of common materials. In trusses of tubes, strain is more important and curves follow a slope (metric) typically close to $E\varepsilon^2$. Trusses of solid rods require a greater combination of modulus and strain,

however, strain is not weighted as heavily with low strain slopes typically close to $E\varepsilon^{1.5}$. Solid rod trusses with lower modulus struts (S2) are possible with current materials, but efficient trusses with higher modulus M60J struts are not feasible with existing materials.

Even though trusses of solid rods are less conducive to the concentrated strain approach, there is still significant motivation to develop them. Solid rods are generally much lower cost and package more compactly than tubes.

Table 1: Materials used in deployable structures and flexure hinges.

Material	Plot Name	E (Gpa)	ε (%)	ρ (kg/m ³)	Deployed				Dist. Strain $\frac{(E\varepsilon)^{2/3}}{\rho}$	Concentrated Strain	
					E/ρ (*10 ⁶)	$\frac{E^{1/2}}{\rho}$	$\frac{E^{3/5}}{\rho}$	$\frac{E^{2/3}}{\rho}$		$E\varepsilon^{1.5}$	$E\varepsilon^2$
AS4/997 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=60%) ¹	AS4	122	1.53	1,589	77.2	220	2,833	15,544	958	232	28.7
E-glass/GPP45 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=45%) ¹	E	30.0	1.55	1,881	15.9	92	1,028	5,133	319	58	7.18
HR40/350 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=60%) ¹	HR	197	0.94	1,630	120	272	3,663	20,736	923	179	17.3
IM7/977-3 Unidirectional (Fv=62%) ¹	IM	154	1.17	1,586	96.9	247	3,249	18,095	935	196	21.2
M46J/2020 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=60%) ¹	M46J	218	0.69	1,650	132	283	3,850	21,944	798	126	10.5
S2-449/SP381 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=50%) ¹	S2	49.2	3.68	1,850	26.6	120	1,406	7,258	803	347	66.6
T300/F655 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=55 to 59%) ¹	T3	143	1.55	1,570	90.9	241	3,139	17,395	1,079	274	34.1
T800/MTM49-3 Unidirectional Prepreg (Fv=60%) ¹	T8	162	1.36	1,620	100	248	3,283	18,346	1,046	257	30.0
Al 7075-T6 ²	Al	71.7	0.70	2,810	25.5	95	1,160	6,142	225	42	3.53
NiTi SMA ²	NT	72.0	5.00	6,500	11.1	41	503	2,663	361	805	180
Steel/Elastomeric Resin ³	SS/ER	86.0	4.00	3,926	21.9	75	926	4,963	580	688	138
IM7/Elastomeric Resin ³	IM/ER	110	4.00	1,500	73.3	221	2,810	15,305	1,790	880	176
S2/Elastomeric Resin ³	S2/ER	35.0	4.00	1,770	19.8	106	1,198	6,045	707	280	56.0
M60J/Elastomeric Resin	M60/ER	237	4.00	1,558	152	312	4,288	24,581	2,875	1,896	379
M60J/Epoxy ³	M60	354	0.70	1,682	211	354	5,055	29,763	1,089	207	17.4
Spring Steel ²	SS	210	1.31	7,850	26.8	58	792	4,501	250	315	36.0
Quartz, Saint-Gobain ³	Qrtz	45.0	3.43	1,844	24.4	115	1,337	6,861	724	286	52.9
P-120S/Epoxy ³	P120	498	0.29	1,826	273	386	5,710	34,389	702	78	4.23
K13D2U/Epoxy ³	K13	560	0.36	1,844	304	406	6,069	36,839	865	121	7.26

¹Prospector:Composites, Developed by Firehole Technologies Inc. and hosted by IDES Inc., <http://www.ides.com/prospector/composites.asp>.

²Matweb, Automation Creations Inc., <http://www.matweb.com/>.

³Rule of mixtures using manufacturer datasheets.

Figure 5: Comparison of the structural mass efficiency of materials used in mechanical and material deformation based deployable structures.

Figure 6: Specific modulus or modulus and density plots vs. strain for a) distributed strain and b) concentrated strain structures.

Figure 7: A concentrated strain a) truss of tubes¹⁶ and b) truss of solid rods^{17,18}.

Figure 8: Modulus vs. strain plots for concentrated strain trusses of solid rods and tubes in a) beam applications and b) column applications.

FUTURE LARGE STRAIN MATERIALS

The strain data used to generate Figure 6 and Figure 8 are subject to criticism because they represent standardized test results, not laminate high strain bending test results. References 19 and 20 indicate thin composite bending failure strains are actually greater than standardized compressive or tensile tests results. These references also show strengthening with thinning. There is a need for higher strain materials as well as test methods and failure models to engineer flexure hinges made from these materials.

One approach to achieving passive (no heating required) large strain materials currently under investigation is to exploit microbuckling in composites with large strain (100-300%) elastomeric matrix materials. Under tensile or small compressive loads and prior to microbuckling, straight fibers will generate considerable axial stiffness and result in efficient materials for deployed structures. With larger compressive loads, fibers will microbuckle and the elastomeric matrix will allow for large effective compressive strains. Lower matrix stiffness will result in a lower bulk material compressive strength. Even so, the Euler column buckling load of fibers in the absence of a matrix is significant and can provide a useful strength for a deployed structure. Consider an array of steel fibers (e.g. small diameter music wire) in a large strain silicone or polyurethane

matrix at 40% fiber volume fraction. This material is referred to here as steel composite or steel/elastomeric resin. Assume the fibers microbuckle under compressive loads with a wavelength that is 50 times the fiber diameter. Microbuckling will allow large effective elastic strains (approximately 4%) in this composite material while maintaining a compressive strength of 5.18 MPa. If the matrix stiffness is assumed to increase the fiber Euler buckling load by a factor of four, the material strength would be 20.7 MPa. These results are independent of fiber diameter.

Similar materials have been demonstrated with carbon fibers and are shown in Figure 9. While this example uses T300 fibers, materials based on higher modulus fibers are also conceivable and are shown in Table 1 and the metric plots. As shown in Figure 6, such materials have the potential to offer dramatically improved performance and eliminate strain induced architectural limitations.

Understanding the matrix stiffness vs. strain vs. compressive strength requirements of this approach and if it has the potential to be a better hinge material are the subject of ongoing research. The concentrated strain metrics in Table 1 indicate the approach is significantly better than existing materials.

Figure 9: Carbon fibers embedded in a high strain elastomeric resin, a) folded, b) unfolded and c) showing microbuckled wavelength (residual microbuckling is primarily due to resin shrinkage during curing, coupon fabricated by Adherent Technologies, Inc.)

CONCLUSIONS

History has demonstrated the success of carbon and S2 glass fiber composite materials in relatively simple distributed strain deployable structures. Concentrated strain

deployable structures that use less efficient flexible materials only in hinge locations have the potential for greater efficiency, design freedom and compact packaging. However, their implementation is limited by the low strain capacity of engineering materials. These limitations could be eased with both, a better knowledge of the foldability of currently available composite materials and the development of passive high strain materials that exploit elastomeric resins and microbuckling.

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